

Changing Face of Science Communication

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1.

Let me begin the talk with a paper by Stephen Hawking, the well-known theoretical physicist. Last year, he had a totally new idea about black holes. And he wrote a paper. Instead of sending it to a journal editor, he sent it to arXiv. Nothing strange. That is what most high energy physicists do.

22 Jan 2014

[arXiv:1401.5761 \[hep-th\] 22Jan2014](https://arxiv.org/abs/1401.5761)

Information Preservation and Weather Forecasting for Black Holes

S. W. Hawking¹

¹DAMTP, University of Cambridge, UK

Abstract

It has been suggested [1] that the resolution of the information paradox for evaporating black holes is that the holes are surrounded by firewalls, bolts of outgoing radiation that would destroy any infalling observer. Such firewalls would break the CPT invariance of quantum gravity and seem to be ruled out on other

grounds. A different resolution of the paradox is proposed, namely that gravitational collapse produces apparent horizons but no event horizons behind which information is lost. This proposal is supported by ADS-CFT and is the only resolution of the paradox compatible with CPT. The collapse to form a black hole will in general be chaotic and the dual CFT on the boundary of ADS will be turbulent. Thus, like weather forecasting on Earth, information will effectively be lost, although there would be no loss of unitarity.

2.

23 Jan 2014

The very next day **inSPIRE** presented it with a better look and with some added information.

Information Preservation and Weather Forecasting for Black Holes

[S.W. Hawking](#) (Cambridge U., DAMTP)

Jan 22, 2014 - 4 pages

e-Print: [arXiv:1401.5761](#) [hep-th] | [PDF](#)

Abstract (arXiv)

It has been suggested [1] that the resolution of the information paradox for evaporating black holes is that the holes are surrounded by firewalls, bolts of outgoing radiation that would destroy any infalling observer. Such firewalls would break the CPT invariance of quantum gravity and seem to be ruled out on other grounds. A different resolution of the paradox is proposed, namely that gravitational collapse produces apparent horizons but no event horizons behind which information is lost. This proposal is supported by ADS-CFT and is the only resolution of the paradox compatible

with CPT. The collapse to form a black hole will in general be chaotic and the dual CFT on the boundary of ADS will be turbulent. Thus, like weather forecasting on Earth, information will effectively be lost, although there would be no loss of unitarity.

Keyword(s): INSPIRE: [gravitation: collapse](#) | [invariance: CPT](#) | [field theory: conformal](#) | [black hole](#) | [horizon](#) | [information theory](#) | [quantum gravity](#) | [turbulence](#) | [unitarity](#) | [duality](#) | [chaos](#)

Record added 2014-01-23, last modified 2014-05-23

24 Jan 2014

Two days after the arXiv publication, *Nature* commented on the paper. *Nature* had included some material gathered from an interview with Prof. Hawking.

3.

Nature | News

Stephen Hawking: 'There are no black holes'

Notion of an 'event horizon', from which nothing can escape, is incompatible with quantum theory, physicist claims.

[Zeeya Merali](#)

24 January 2014

Nature DOI: [doi:10.1038/nature.2014.14583](https://doi.org/10.1038/nature.2014.14583)

“There is no escape from a black hole in classical theory, but quantum theory enables energy and information to escape.”

The paper was based on a talk he gave via Skype at a meeting at the Kavli Institute for Theoretical Physics in Santa Barbara, California, in August 2013 ([watch video of the talk](#)).

24 January 2014

New Scientist

<http://www.newscientist.com/article/dn24937-stephen-hawkings-new-theory-offers-black-hole-escape.html#.VQDS6U0frIU>

Stephen Hawking's new theory offers black hole escape

16:20 24 January 2014 by [Jacob Aron](#)
For similar stories, visit the [Cosmology](#) Topic Guide

[Read full article](#)

Continue reading page |1|2

Stephen Hawking has a new mind-bending theory about black holes, the bizarre cosmic objects that cemented his reputation as the world's most famous living scientist. Rather than getting sucked into a singularity of confusion, read our [explainer](#).

Is he right? Is the paradox solved?

Hawking's paper is very short, just two pages of text with no calculations, making it difficult to draw any strong conclusions, but there is already some scepticism. "It is not clear what he expects the infalling observer to see," says Polchinski. "It almost sounds like he is replacing the firewall with a chaos-wall, which could be the same thing." [Samuel Braunstein](#) of the University of York, UK, who has [waded into the firewall debate previously](#), also isn't convinced: "I don't see any evidence which really demonstrates that the thing he is talking about doesn't have a firewall."

4.

Then the floodgate opened. Within the next few days many stories appeared in the press – newspapers and magazines, radio and TV channels. Many scientists

commented on Hawking's paper, and started citing it in their own papers and blogs. For a science story, the interest it generated in both conventional and social media was truly amazing.

It even led to some humour as seen from this *New Yorker* piece by comedian Andy Borowitz.

*Stephen **Hawking's** Blunder on **Black Holes** Shows Danger of ...*

January 27, 2014 Stephen **Hawking's** Blunder on **Black Holes** Shows Danger of Listening to Scientists, Says Bachmann By Andy Borowitz

[BOROWITZ REPORT](#)

JANUARY 27, 2014

Stephen Hawking's Blunder on Black Holes Shows Danger of Listening to Scientists, Says Bachmann

BY [ANDY BOROWITZ](#)

WASHINGTON ([The Borowitz Report](#))—Dr. Stephen Hawking’s recent statement that the black holes he famously described do not actually exist underscores “the danger inherent in listening to scientists,” Rep. Michele Bachmann (R-Minnesota) said today.

Rep. Bachmann unleashed a blistering attack on Dr. Hawking, who earlier referred to his mistake on black holes as his “biggest blunder.”

“Actually, Dr. Hawking, our biggest blunder as a society was ever listening to people like you,” said Rep. Bachmann. “If black holes don’t exist, then other things you scientists have been trying to foist on us probably don’t either, like climate change and evolution.”

Rep. Bachmann added that all the students who were forced to learn about black holes in college should now sue Dr. Hawking for a full refund. “Fortunately for me, I did not take any science classes in college,” she said.

Bachmann’s anti-Hawking comments seemed to be gaining traction on Capitol Hill, as seen from the statement by Rep. Lamar Smith (R-Texas), Chairman of the House Science Committee, who said, “Going forward,

members of the House Science Committee will do our best to avoid listening to scientists.”

Andy Borowitz is a *New York Times* best-selling author and a comedian who has written for *The New Yorker* since 1998. He writes the [Borowitz Report](#) for newyorker.com.

27 Jan 2014

There was also some serious accusations.

In the Australian website 'iceinspace', Bojan questions Nature's coverage of Hawking's paper in arXiv and even accuses **Nature of slowing down the progress of science by paying importance to individuals rather than the truth of what is said** (by anyone).

5.

The paper received enormous media coverage – both print and electronic, and much more in social media – within a week. A search on the web brought this long list (shown only a small part of it):

Stephen Hawking: 'There are no black holes' : Nature News ...

Stephen **Hawking**: 'There are **no black holes**' Notion of an 'event horizon', from which nothing can escape, is incompatible with quantum theory, physicist claims. Zeeya Merali; 24 **January 2014**. Article tools Rights & Permissions.

nature.com/news/stephen-hawking-there-are-no-black-h...

*BBC - Future - Stephen **Hawking's** new **black hole** theory*

Share this with **Digg** ; Share this with Facebook ; Share this with Google ; ... 29 **January 2014** Designer drugs "concocted in labs by tweaking a few atoms here and there" are novel and legal. ... Stephen**Hawking**: There are **no black holes** Zeeya Merali | Nature ...

bbc.com/future/story/20140203-hawkings-new-black-...

*Stephen **Hawking's** new theory offers **black hole** escape*

... Stephen **Hawking's** new theory offers **black hole** escape - physics-math - 24 **January 2014** ... **Digg** this Thread! Add Thread to del.icio.us; ... A brief history of **black holes** - space - 28 **January 2014** ...

thescienceforum.com/astrophysics-cosmology/41307-stephen-hawking...

*Stephen **Hawking** boldly claims there are **no black holes***

Stephen **Hawking** boldly claims there are **no black holes** by: ... **January 26, 2014** 7:57AM; Increase Text Size; Decrease Text Size; Print; Email; Share. Add to **Digg**; Add to del.icio.us; Add to Facebook; Add to Kwoff; ... "There is **no** escape from a **black hole** in classical theory," **Hawking** ...

news.com.au/technology/science/stephen-hawking-boldly...

*Stephen **Hawking**: "The Absence of Event Horizons Means There ...*

January 26, 2014 in Science. by Logan. Recommend on Facebook; Tweet about it; **Digg** this post; share via Reddit; Email [But quantum theory] enables energy and information to escape from a **black hole**,"**Hawking** told Nature.

planet.infowars.com/science/stephen-hawking-the-absence-of-ev...

*Stephen **Hawking**: There Are **No Black Holes***

Famed astrophysicist Stephen **Hawking** declares 'there are **no black holes**' in a new preprint paper, ... The very basis of this burning issue is the thing that makes **black holes black** — the event horizon. ... Copyright © **2014** All Rights Reserved. ...

space.com/24418-stephen-hawking-no-black-holes.html

***No Black Holes** Exist, Says Stephen **Hawking**--At Least Not Like ...*

Theoretical physicist Leonard Susskind at Stanford University in California, who also did not take part in**Hawking's** research, suggests there may be another solution to the conundrums that **black holes** pose.

news.nationalgeographic.com/news/2014/01/140127-black-hole-stephen-ha...

***Black hole** theory my 'biggest blunder,' Stephen **Hawking** says ...*

Stephen **Hawking** now says light and information may be able to escape from **black holes**, ... Stephen**Hawking** now says light and information may be able to escape from **black holes**, ... Published **January 26,2014**. FoxNews.com. Facebook 0 Twitter 0 livefyre Email Print. April 9, ...

foxnews.com/science/2014/01/26/stephen-hawking-contradict...

*Stephen **Hawking**: There are '**NO**' **Black Holes**..!*

... ThinkStock PROFESSOR Stephen **Hawking** has shocked the scientific community by radically claiming there are **no black holes**. In an Register; Help ... 6 hours ago **January 25, 2014** 5:36PM It's a **black hole**, ... questions 40 years after **Hawking's** first papers on **black holes** and information is ...

projectavalon.net/forum4/showthread.php?67761-Stephen-Hawki...

*Stephen **Hawking**: **Black Holes** May Not Have 'Event Horizons ...*

... 01/25/2014 11:59 am EST ... **Hawking** posted his paper on the arXiv preprint server on 22 **January** 1, and it has yet to pass peer review. He titled it, whimsically, ... Stephen **Hawking's** Universe: **Black Hole** Time : Video : Discovery ...

huffingtonpost.com/2014/01/24/stephen-hawking-black-holes-ev...

*Stephen **Hawking**: "There Are **No Black Holes**" - Scientific American*

"There is **no** escape from a **black hole** in classical theory," **Hawking** told Nature. Quantum theory, ... Although Page accepts **Hawking's** proposal that a **black hole** could exist without an event ... The article was first published on **January 24, 2014**. Share this Article: Comments You ...

 scientificamerican.com/article/stephen-hawking-there-are-no-blac...

*Stephen **Hawking's** new theory offers **black hole** escape ...*

Stephen **Hawking's** new theory offers **black hole** escape. 16:20 24 **January 2014** by ... **Hawking** applied quantum theory to **black holes** and ... Other theorists suggested solving this "information paradox" by allowing information to escape from the **black hole** as it evaporated. **Hawking** ...

newsscientist.com/article/dn24937-stephen-hawkings-new-theo...

*Grey is the new **black hole**: is Stephen **Hawking** right?*

... the media has cried out the recent proclamation from Stephen **Hawking** that **black holes**, a mystery of both science and ... General Physics; **January 29, 2014**; Grey is the new **black hole**: is Stephen **Hawking**right? Jan 29, **2014** by Geraint Lewis, The Conversation . Enlarge. Stephen **Hawking** stirs ...

phys.org/news/2014-01-grey-black-hole-stephen-hawk...

*Stephen **Hawking** declares: 'There are **no black holes**' - CNET*

Stephen **Hawking** declares: 'There are **no black holes**' ... **January 25, 2014** 2:26 PM PST; comments. 0; facebook. twitter. linkedin. googleplus. more. more + email. tumblr. stumble. reddit. pinterest. ... Wait, so my life may not have disappeared down a **black hole** after all?

cnet.com/news/stephen-hawking-declares-there-are-n...

*Prison Planet.com » Stephen **Hawking's** new research ...*

Exactly 40 years after famed theoretical physicist Stephen **Hawking** brought event horizons and **blackholes** into the public eye, ... towards the **black hole**. It is, in other words, ... This article was posted: Tuesday, **January 28, 2014** at 6:28 am. Share this article; Recommend on Facebook;

 prisonplanet.com/stephen-hawkings-new-research-there-are-n...

*Stephen **Hawking** on **Black Holes** and Why He'd Be a Good Bond ...*

Stephen **Hawking** always starts his lectures with the same quip: ... in **January 2014**, was titled "Information preservation and weather forecasting for **black holes**") ... The experiment I would like performed is to detect **Hawking** radiation from a **black hole**, ...

wired.com/2015/01/stephen-hawking-black-holes-hed-g...

*Stephen **Hawking's** Blunder on **Black Holes** Shows Danger of ...*

January 27, 2014 Stephen **Hawking's** Blunder on **Black Holes** Shows Danger of Listening to Scientists, Says Bachmann By Andy Borowitz

 newyorker.com/humor/borowitz-report/stephen-hawkings-bl...

*Stephen **Hawking** - Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia*

In **January 2014** he called the alleged loss of information in **black holes** his "biggest blunder". As part of ...**Hawking** appeared in documentaries entitled The Real Stephen **Hawking** (2001), ... **Hawking**, S. W. (1974). "**Black hole** explosions?".

W en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Stephen_Hawking

*The Reference Frame: Bizarre **Hawking**: **black hole** work was my ...*

... the reason why we don't revert the picture above upside down is that it is simply extremely unlikely for a **black hole**, an object, to "emit" a **Hawking** radiation that looks like a star. ... **January** (42) **2014** (519) December (39) November (48) October (52)

motls.blogspot.com/2014/01/bizarre-hawking-black-hole-work-w...

*bensozia: Stephen **Hawking** Rethinks **Black Holes***

Friday, **January 24, 2014**. Stephen **Hawking** Rethinks **Black Holes** **Black holes** are one of the places that our two models of the universe, quantum mechanics and general relativity, ... In general relativity, for an unchanging **black hole**, ...

benedante.blogspot.com/2014/01/stephen-hawking-rethinks-black-ho...

[1401.5761] Information Preservation and Weather Forecasting ...

... Information Preservation and Weather Forecasting for **Black Holes**. Authors: S. W. **Hawking** (Submitted on 22 Jan **2014**) Abstract: ... The collapse to form a **black hole** will in general be chaotic and the dual CFT on the boundary of ADS will be turbulent.

arxiv.org/abs/1401.5761

*Terra Forming Terra: Stephen **Hawking**: 'There are **No Black Holes**'*

24 **January 2014**. <http://www.nature.com/news/stephen-hawking-there-are-no-black-holes-1.14583#auth-1>.

globalwarming-arclein.blogspot.com/2015/03/stephen-hawking-there-are-no-blac...

*"There Are **No Black Holes**" - The Hazards of Selective ...*

"There Are **No Black Holes**" ... Posted by stuart on Mar 17th, **2014** and filed under H. Bruce Rinker, Ph.D., Perspective. You can follow any responses to this entry through the RSS 2.0. You can ... Recently, Stephen**Hawking** ...

theroanokestar.com/2014/03/17/there-are-no-black-holes-the-h...

*Stephen **Hawking** Says **No Black Holes** Exist*

Stephen **Hawking** is the most famous living scientist in the world and he gained much of his notoriety from the bizarre space objects known as "**black holes**."

 guardianlv.com/2014/01/stephen-hawking-says-no-black-hol...

*Stephen **Hawking**: 'There are **no black holes**' - Science News ...*

Stephen **Hawking**: 'There are **no black holes**' Started by michel123456, Jan 26, **2014** . Page 1 of 2 ; 1; 2; Next; Please log in to reply; 22 replies to this topic

 scienceforums.net/topic/81463-stephen-hawking-there-are-no-...

***Hawking**, co-discoverer of **black holes**, now says there's **no** such thing...*

Pinterest. LinkedIn. **Digg**. "The absence of event horizons means that there are **no black holes** — in the sense of regimes from which light can't escape to infinity," **Hawking** writes.

mike-ro-tech.com/blog/hawking-co-discoverer-of-black-holes...

*Stephen Hawking: ...of Event Horizons Means There are **No Black Holes***

January 25, 2014. Stephen **Hawking**: "The Absence of Event Horizons Means There are **No Black Holes**". [But quantum theory] enables energy and information to escape from a **black hole**," **Hawking** told Nature.

dailygalaxy.com/my_weblog/2014/01/stephen-hawking-there-a...

*Stephen Hawking: 'There are **no black holes**' - Space News - Astronomy...*

Edited by Ryu, 25 **January 2014** - 02:29 PM. I don't think Dr. **Hawking** is saying there are **no black holes** that endlessly suck everything just that we must rethink our ideas about the event horizon.

unexplained-mysteries.com/forum/index.php?showtopic=261377

*Did Hawking Say "There Are **No Black Holes**"? / Of Particular Significance*

But did **Hawking** really say "There are **no black holes**", or didn't he?? Talk about taking things out of context!!! Here's what **Hawking** actually said. Pingback: Allgemeines Live-Blog vom 25. Januar **2014** | Skyweek Zwei Punkt Null.

profmattstrassler.com/2014/01/30/did-hawking-say-there-are-no-b...

*Stephen Hawking Published a Paper Claiming There Are **No Black Holes**...*

By Jia Tolentino | **January 27, 2014.** **Hawking's** theory addresses Joseph Polchinski's "**black-hole** firewall paradox, which has been vexing physicists for almost two years."

thehairpin.com/2014/01/stephen-hawking-just-published-a-...

*Hawking now says there are **no black holes**? / Uncommon Descent*

Black holes made him famous, right? **Hawking** radiation and all. Anyway, he says now, there are **no blackholes** as we understand them. bornagain77 **January 24, 2014** at 4:43 pm. Stephen **Hawking** has lost all the great respect I had for him when he wrote 'The Grand Design'.

uncommondescent.com/cosmology/hawking-now-says-there-are-no-b...

*Stephen Hawking Proposes: "There Are **No Black Holes**" (January 27, 2014)*

January 27, 2014 by zazenlife 1 Comment. Most physicists foolhardy enough to write a paper claiming that "there are **no black holes**" In place of the event horizon, **Hawking** invokes an "apparent horizon", a surface along which light rays attempting to rush away from the **black hole's** core will be suspended.

zazenlife.com/2014/01/27/no-black-holes-stephen-hawking/

*Stephen Hawking: 'There are **no black holes**' / Forum*

Stephen **Hawking**: 'There are **no black holes**'. Notion of an 'event horizon', from which nothing can escape, is incompatible with quantum theory, physicist claims. 24 **January 2014** Artist's impression VICTOR HABBICK VISIONS/SPL/Getty.

wikileaks-forum.com/the-starry-skies/594/-stephen-hawking-the...

*Stephen Hawking: 'There Are **no Black Holes**' - Technology News... / Forum*

By Chris Matyszczyk **January 25, 2014** 2:26 PM PST Consternation and angst reign after the famed physicist suggests there are **no black holes** from which light can't escape to infinity.

nsaneforums.com/topic/204078-stephen-hawking-there-are-no...

*Stephen Hawking says there are **no black holes** / Oddly Even*

Posted on **January 24, 2014** by oddly. "The absence of event horizons mean that there are **no black holes**— in the sense of regimes from which light can't escape to infinity," writes **Hawking**, in a new paper.

> [oddy-even.com/2014/01/24/stephen-hawking-says-there-are...](http://oddy-even.com/2014/01/24/stephen-hawking-says-there-are-...)

PDF Stephen Hawking: 'There are no black holes'

10/7/2014 Stephen **Hawking**: 'There are **no black holes**' : Nature News & Comment Page 2 of 19 modern **black-hole** theory, does away with the notion of an event "The correct treatment," **Hawking** says, "remains a mystery." **Hawking** posted his paper on the arXiv preprint server on 22 January 1.

> astronomy.sierracollege.edu/Courses/Astronomy25/papers/Hawking1.pdf

Stephen Hawking Claims There Are No Black Holes?

Added by Kimberly Ruble on **January 25, 2014**. Stephen **Hawking** is claiming there are **no black holes**. His new theory is based on a new paper he wrote that claims the event horizon of a **black hole** does not exist.

 guardianlv.com/2014/01/stephen-hawking-claims-there-are-...

Today.Az - Stephen Hawking: There are no black holes

Stephen **Hawking**: There are **no black holes**. 27 **January 2014** [14:06] - TODAY.AZ. The physicist claims, in a paper posted online Wednesday, that the idea of an event horizon—the point of **no** return at a **blackhole**—conflicts with quantum theory.

today.az/news/interesting/130340.html

Black Holes No More? Not Quite. / ITS RUF January 25, 2014, 3:30 PM

Black Holes No More? Not Quite. by Brian Koberlein. on **January 24, 2014**. Nature News has announced that there are **no black holes**. This claim is made by none other than Stephen **Hawking**, so does this mean **black holes** are **no** more?

 universetoday.com/108561/black-holes-no-more-not-quite/

According to Stephen Hawking 'There are no black holes' - RSI Community...

Posted: **January 2014**. thought he was arguing against the existence of the event horizon..... wouldn't be the first time he was wrong about **black holes** though. Posted: **January 2014**. I do sometimes wonder if **Hawking** is just taking the piss, as he knows what ever he says will be published.

forums.robertsspaceindustries.com/discussion/100192/according-to-stephen-ha...

What did Stephen Hawking Really Say about Black Holes ? / Astrosplash

Posted on **January 28, 2014** by apatrano. Many of us have recently seen in the media the shocking news that Stephen **Hawking** has claimed that "there are **no black holes**".

apatrano.wordpress.com/2014/01/28/what-did-stephen-hawking-reall...

Stephen Hawking's new research: 'There are no black holes' / ExtremeTech

By Sebastian Anthony on **January 27, 2014** at 9:48 am. In a short research paper (arXiv:1401.5761) called "Information Preservation and Weather Forecasting for **Black Holes**," **Hawking** proposes that **black holes** are instead enveloped by an apparent horizon.

extremetech.com/extreme/175414-stephen-hawking-research-t...

Hawking proposes new interpretation of black holes / Forum

25th **January 2014**, 07:56 AM #1. Steven **Hawking** has proposed a radical new theory of the **black hole**. I don't fully understand the paradox he was attempting to solve, but it stems from the disconnect between general relativity and quantum mechanics in some way.

volconvo.com/forums/science-technology/45014-hawking-p...

*Event Horizons, **Black Holes**, **Hawking**, Reality, Illusion*

Black Holes. January 26, 2014. No Black Holes Exist, Says Stephen Hawking - At Least Not Like We Think National Geographic - **January 27, 2014 Black holes** do not exist - at least, not as we know them, says renowned physicist Stephen **Hawking**, potentially provoking a rethink of one of space's most...

crystalinks.com/blackholes.114.html

*Alt-week 01.26.14: **Hawking** says there are **no black holes**, and a 3D printed...*

Hawking applied quantum theory to **black holes**, and calculated some radiation should be emitted, eventually causing them to shrink and die -- something that, again contradicts the popular belief that they are immortal.

engadget.com/2014/01/26/alt-week-01-26-14/

*Stephen **Hawking**: 'There are **no black holes**' [Space] - Time for Science*

"There is **no** escape from a **black hole** in classical theory," **Hawking** told Nature. **Hawking** posted his paper on the arXiv preprint server on 22 **January**. He titled it, whimsically, 'Information preservation and weather forecasting for **black holes**', and it has yet to pass peer review.

pcbheaven.com/opendir/index.php?show=69112tr71560osa6bc...

*Hot off the Press...Stephen **Hawking**: 'There are **no black holes**' | Forum*

Stephen **Hawking**: 'There are **no black holes**'. Notion of an 'event horizon', from which nothing can escape, is incompatible with quantum theory, physicist claims. Last edited by Heretic; 26th **January 2014** at 14:09.

hexusnow.info/forum/showthread.php?15252-Hot-off-the-Pr...

*There are **no Black Holes** (apparently) - Overclockers Australia Forums*

Search our forums with Google: Thread Tools. 25th **January 2014**, 8:26 PM. PROFESSOR Stephen**Hawking** has shocked the scientific community by radically claiming there are **no black holes**.

forums.overclockers.com.au/showthread.php?p=15878163

*Stephen **Hawking** admits 'there are **no black holes** - but there are GREY holes...*

Stephen **Hawking** stuns physicists by declaring 'there are **no black holes**' - but says there are GREY ones. Author claims there is **no** 'event horizon' **black hole**. Published: 20:57 GMT, 24 **January 2014** | Updated: 09:35 GMT, 25 **January 2014**.

dailymail.co.uk/sciencetech/article-2545552/Stephen-Hawki...

*Stephen **Hawking** says there is **no such thing as black holes**, Einstein spinning...*

Published: 17:35, Fri, **January 24, 2014**. Professor Stephen **Hawking** says **black holes** do not exist [WENN]. The wheelchair-bound genius has posted a paper online that demolishes modern **black hole** theory.

express.co.uk/life-style/science-technology/455880/Step...

*Stephen **Hawking** now thinks "there are **no black holes**"*

by Ian Steadman Published 27 **January, 2014** - 18:22. But that's what "Information Preservation and Weather Forecasting for **Black Holes**", the study **Hawking** published last week on arXiv, says: "there are **no black holes**".

newstatesman.com/future-proof/2014/01/stephen-hawking-now-...

*Stephen **Hawking** declares: 'There are **no black holes**' | Donna Murdoch...*

Posted on **January 25, 2014** by Donna Murdoch. "...now, in a new paper called "Information Preservation and Weather Forecasting for **Black Holes**," Stephen **Hawking** has cast the cat among the **black**, holey pigeons and caused a scattering of incomprehension.

donnamurdoch.com/2014/01/25/stephen-hawking-declares-there...

[Скачать песни Muse в MP3 бесплатно - музыкальная подборка и альбомы...](#)

Black Holes and Revelations (2006) 2 июля 2006 г. Muse выпустила 4-й студийный альбом «**BlackHoles** and Revelations». Первый сингл с альбома, «Supermassive **Black Hole**», был выпущен как звуковая загрузка 9 мая 2006 и сопровождался клипом, снятым Floria Sigismondi.

zaycev.net/artist/73286

[Prof. **Hawking** Says There Are **No Black Holes** \(Video\) | Space](#)

Sunday, **January 26, 2014** 7:25. % of readers think this story is Fact. (N.Morgan) World Renowned Professor **Hawking** shocked physicists by saying there's **no black holes**. He went on to explain that he thinks there are grey **holes**.

beforeitsnews.com/space/2014/01/prof-hawking-says-there-are...

[Stephen **Hawking** Says There Are **No Black Holes** | Giant Freakin RobotGiant...](#)

Date: Sep 13, **2014** | Category: Sci-Fi, Sci-Fi In Real Life. Scientists Working To Help Stephen **Hawking** Communicate. Also, that was an artificial **black hole** created with red matter, those don't follow the same physics as **Hawking's black holes**...

giantfreakinrobot.com/sci/stephen-hawking-black-holes.html

[Interactions: **January High Five \(2014\)** | Altmetric.com](#)

"Information Preservation and Weather Forecasting for **Black Holes**" (**Hawking**) Submitted to arXiv on 22**January 2014**. According to Professor Stephen **Hawking**, **black holes** are actually not how we imagine them to be (or even how he imagined them to be...

altmetric.com/blog/interactions-january-high-five-2014/

[newdaynews.com/](#)

[**January**] after graduation fr.

newdaynews.com

[Stephen **Hawking** Bombshell: "**Black Holes, As We Know Them, Do Not Exist**"](#)

January 28, 2014 News. Stephen **Hawking**, the British physicist who is well known for the discovery of **Hawking** Radiation, recently published a new paper that turned our conventional perception of **blackholes** on its head.

fromquarkstoquasars.com/stephen-hawking-bombshell-black-holes-as...

[quantum gravity - Why does Stephen **Hawking** say **black holes** don't exist?...](#)

Article in Nature News: Stephen **Hawking**: "There are **no black holes**" (Zeeya Merali, **January 24, 2014**). "Most physicists foolhardy enough to write a paper claiming that "there are **no black holes**"...would probably be dismissed as cranks".

physics.stackexchange.com/questions/95366/why-does-stephen-hawking-...

[Slooh Live Events](#)

Black Hole Overhead: Canary Islands - September 12, 2013.

live.slooh.com/stadium/live-universe-january-27-2014

[What Stephen **Hawking** Really Said About **Black Holes** | Hip Hop News](#)

April 18, 2014blogAbout, **Black, Hawking, Holes, REALLY, Said, Stephen**admin. Hank explains the science behind recent reports that physics great Stephen **Hawking** said "there are **no black holes**." There are.

> edwardsinternationalinc.info/blog/what-stephen-hawking-really-said-abo...

[Stephen Hawking Black holes are... Grey Holes - Science! Astronomy & Space...](#)

The **black hole** paradox is real dilemma. **Hawking** has been trying to come up with a solution for years. Hawkins has shown in theory how **black holes** shrink/evaporate by means of Hawkins radiation, Now if it's radiating out quantum particles and eating matter I can see where the EH...

cloudynights.com/topic/450136-stephen-hawking-black-holes-...

[Stephen Hawking Says Black Holes Don't Exist \(Sort Of\) - D-brief](#)

By Bill Andrews | **January 29, 2014** 1:53 pm. If there's one thing in physics that captures peoples' imagination (besides time travel), it's **black holes**. **Black Hole** Bio. "There are **no black holes**," **Hawking** writes in a recent paper.

blogs.discovermagazine.com/d-brief/2014/01/29/stephen-hawking-says-b...

[Hawking proposes new theory on black holes - The Hindu](#)

Washington, **January 24, 2014**. **Hawking's** new suggestion is that the 'apparent horizon' is the real boundary. "The absence of event horizons mean that there are **no black holes** — in the sense of regimes from which light can not escape to infinity," Prof.

thehindu.com/sci-tech/science/hawking-proposes-new-the...

[CR4 - Blog Entry: Stephen Hawking Says There Are No Black Holes](#)

Posted **January 25, 2014** 6:43 PM. From Popular Science With **no** event horizons, there are **no blackholes**, according to **Hawking**.

 cr4.globalspec.com/blogentry/24100/Stephen-Hawking-Says-Ther...

[Plugging the hole in Hawking's black hole theory](#)

On **January 24**, the journal Nature published an article entitled "There are **no black holes**." It doesn't take much to spark controversy in the world of physics... Grey is the new **black hole**: is Stephen **Hawking** right? Jan 29, **2014**.

phys.org/news/2014-03-hole-hawking-black-theory.html

[Stephen Hawking rejects the idea of a black hole - The Sphinx Stargate](#)

January 31, 2014 at 8:17 am. Why **Hawking** changed his mind is explained in his paper and some of the news articles that have links on the Starburst Foundation news posting. It has to do with **Hawking's**realisation that quantum theory is incompatible with the notions of a **black hole** event horizon or **black**...

> etheric.com/stephen-hawking-rejects-idea-black-hole/

[Stephen Hawking: 'There are no black holes' by Zeeya Merali...](#)

Posted on **2014/03/09** by kriti shree. Most physicists foolhardy enough to write a paper claiming that "there are **no black holes**" — at least not in the sense we usually imagine — would probably be dismissed as cranks. **Hawking** posted his paper on the arXiv preprint server on 22 January 1.

> kritisansar.noblogs.org/post/2014/03/09/stephen-hawking-there-are...

[Stephen Hawking: 'There are no black holes' - Knowledge and Culture... / Forum](#)

Stephen **Hawking**: 'There are **no black holes**'. Options. Previous Topic · Next Topic. Christine. Absurdicuss. Posted: Monday, **January 27, 2014** 6:33:48 PM. Rank: Advanced Member.

forum.thefreedictionary.com/postst52346_Stephen-Hawking---There-are-n...

*Hawking Says **Black Holes** Do Not Exist : :: TheGuruReview.net*

January 28, 2014 by Michael | Category: Around The Net. **Hawking's** unpublished work — titled "Information Preservation and Weather Forecasting for **Black Holes**" and uploaded to the arXiv preprint service — declares that "there are **no black holes**."

thegurureview.net/aroundnet-category/hawking-says-black-hol...

*Information Preservation and Weather Forecasting for **Black Holes** | physics4me*

January 24, 2014 physicsgg. This entry was posted in Cosmology, Quantum Physics, Relativity and tagged **Black Holes**, **Hawking**, Stephen **Hawking**.

physicsforme.com/2014/01/24/information-preservation-and-w...

*Shocking Science: There Are **No Black Holes** - Prof **Hawking** / INFORMATION...*

Posted by: niyi January 25, 2014. Professor Stephen **Hawking** has shocked the scientific community, especially physicists, by radically claiming there are **no black holes**.

 informationng.com/2014/01/shocking-science-there-are-no-bla...

*Hawkings says "**No black holes**" after Vomit-Comet ride... - Real World... / Forum*

Some time ago, in 2007, young Stephen - of apocryphal **black hole** fame - took a ride in the Vomit-Comet: Well, it seems that the professor has subsequently changed his mind about **black holes** and now questions their existence

forum.mutleysshangar.com/index.php/topic/12268-hawkings-says-no-bl...

*New Theory of Stephen **Hawking** Claims That **Black Holes** Don't Exist*

By Anna LeMind • February 9, 2014 Physics & Natural Sciences, Uncommon Science, Universe. Prominent physicist Stephen **Hawking**, one of the "fathers" of the modern theory of **black holes** In essence, he claims that there are **no black holes**, at least as they are imagined by the scientists so far.

 learning-mind.com/new-theory-of-stephen-hawking-claims-that...

*Stephen **Hawking**: **Black Holes** Don't Really Exist | Geekologie*

January 28, 2014 in beats me, **black hole** sun won't you come wash away the raaaain, **black holes**, event horizon, hmm, mr. know it all, space, stephen **hawking**, the universe, theories, you don't know that for sure!, your guess is as good as mind...

geekologie.com/2014/01/stephen-hawking-black-holes-dont-...

greenbrocade.com/

Delta Force: **Black Hawk** Down PC NOTE...

greenbrocade.com

*Top 10 Facts about the **Black Hole** - List Crux*

By Prasanta Kr Dutta | May 3, 2014 0 Comments. In the words of Stephen **Hawking**, "It is said that fact is sometimes stranger than fiction, and nowhere is this more true than in the case of **black holes**."

 listcrux.com/top-10-facts-black-hole/

*According to Stephen **Hawking**, **black holes** as we currently understand them...*

January 26, 2014 | by Elise Andrew. According to **Hawking**, "The absence of event horizons mean there are **no black holes** - in the sense of regimes from which light can't escape to infinite".

iflscience.com/physics/according-stephen-hawking-black-h...

*How do **black holes** form jets? | Galaxy Zoo*

The supermassive **black holes** at the hearts of galaxies are supposed to be simple. For someone looking at a **black hole** from afar, physicists tell us all **black holes** can be described by just three parameters: their mass, electric... More Like Grey **Holes**, Says **Hawking** - **January 25, 2014**.

blog.galaxyzoo.org/2014/01/22/how-do-black-holes-form-jets/

*Stephen **Hawking** admits "**Black Holes**" don't exist - OSNet Daily*

But now **Hawking's** third theory as to what a **black hole** could look like has got physicists' heads spinning. **Hawking's** new suggestion is that the apparent horizon is the real boundary. 2 osnetdaily **January 29, 2014** Science News.

 osnetdaily.com/2014/01/stephen-hawking-admits-black-hole...

*No, Stephen **Hawking** Did Not Say **Black Holes** Don't Exist | Gizmodo Australia*

All of this stems from a short paper **Hawking** submitted on **January 22**, titled "Information Preservation and Weather Forecasting for **Black Holes**." Timmahh @timmahh. February 2, **2014** 3:51 pm. I believe **Hawking** radiation to be part of this story... As in the radiation that does escape a **black hole**...

gizmodo.com.au/2014/02/no-stephen-hawking-did-not-say-bl...

***Hawking** on **black holes** « Ted Bunn's Blog*

Hawking's proposal is that **black holes** are like the second diagram, not the first one. Now why does this matter? This entry was posted on Friday, **January 31st, 2014** at 4:14 pm and is filed under Uncategorized.

blog.richmond.edu/physicsbunn/2014/01/31/hawking-on-black-h...

*"There Are **No Black Holes**", Says Stephen **Hawking** in New Paper...*

by Anurag · **January 26, 2014**. Instead, in his paper, Information Preservation and Weather Forecasting for **Black Holes**, **Hawking** proposes that **black holes** can exist without "event horizons", the invisible cover believed to surround every **black hole**.

 quirkpost.com/1679/there-are-no-black-holes-says-stephe...

*Stephen **Hawking** **Black Holes** Claims Aren't Real; Renowned Cosmologist...*

By Staff Writer | **January 26, 2014** 09:56 PM EST. There is **no** such thing as **black hole** - this is what famous theoretical physicist, cosmologist, author Stephen **Hawking** told media, opposing the theories he and his colleagues earlier stated.

kpopstarz.com/articles/75970/20140126/stephen-hawking-s...

*Stephen **Hawking**: 'There are **no black holes**' - Science - News...*

Saturday 25 **January 2014**. Instead, in his paper, Information Preservation and Weather Forecasting for **Black Holes**, **Hawking** proposes that **black holes** can exist without 'event horizons', the invisible cover believed to surround every **black hole**.

independent.co.uk/news/science/stephen-hawking-there-are-no...

What do we learn from the **Hawking** paper and its instant dissemination? Within days it was commented by professional journals as well as magazines and newspapers; the electronic media came in too. Many bloggers, including some scientists, pitched in. As a result, thousands of people around the world have come to know about the new development and it led to widespread discussion.

Suppose, Hawking had come up with the same paper some thirty years ago. Would it have received such attention? Certainly not. Why?

There was no web or arXiv then. There was only the traditional way of publishing which was inherently slow and whose reach was small.

5.

Here is another recent paper. This one from the *Genome Biology*

Genome Biology

Expression of multiple horizontally acquired genes is a hallmark of both vertebrate and invertebrate genomes

Alastair Crisp^{1†}, Chiara Boschetti^{1†}, Malcolm Perry¹²³, Alan Tunnacliffe^{1*} and Gos Micklem^{23*}

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For all author emails, please [log on](#).

Genome Biology 2015, **16**:50 doi:10.1186/s13059-015-0607-3

Alastair Crisp and Chiara Boschetti contributed equally to this work.

The electronic version of this article is the complete one and can be found online at:

<http://genomebiology.com/2015/16/1/50>

Received: **25 September 2014**

Accepted: **4 February 2015**

Published: **13 March 2015**

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Abstract

Background

A fundamental concept in biology is that heritable material, DNA, is passed from parent to offspring, a process called vertical gene transfer. An alternative mechanism of gene acquisition is through horizontal gene transfer (HGT), which involves movement of genetic material between different species. HGT is well-known in single-celled organisms such as bacteria, but its existence in higher organisms, including animals, is less well established, and is controversial in humans.

Results

We have taken advantage of the recent availability of a sufficient number of high-quality genomes and associated transcriptomes to carry out a detailed examination of HGT in 26 animal species (10 primates, 12 flies and four nematodes) and a simplified analysis in a further 14 vertebrates. Genome-wide comparative and phylogenetic analyses show that HGT in animals typically gives rise to tens or hundreds of active 'foreign' genes, largely concerned with metabolism. Our analyses suggest that while fruit flies and nematodes have continued to acquire foreign genes throughout their evolution, humans and other primates have gained relatively few since their common ancestor. We also resolve the controversy surrounding previous evidence of HGT in humans and provide at least 33 new examples of horizontally acquired genes.

Conclusions

We argue that HGT has occurred, and continues to occur, on a previously unsuspected scale in metazoans and is likely to have contributed to biochemical diversification during animal evolution.

This paper has also received some attention of the media

Human genome includes 'foreign' genes not from our ancestors ...

Alastair Crisp Media enquiries. Craig ... **Chiara Boschetti**. Places. School of Technology. Department of Chemical Engineering and Biotechnology. Related organisations. ... © 2015 **University of Cambridge**. **University** A-Z; Contact the **University**; Accessibility; Freedom of information;

cam.ac.uk/research/news/human-genome-includes-forei...

Genome Biology / Full text / Expression of multiple ...

Alastair Crisp 1 †, **Chiara Boschetti** 1 ... 3 **Cambridge Systems Biology Centre, University of Cambridge, Cambridge CB2 1QR, UK** ... Sign up to receive new article alerts from **Genome Biology** Sign up. Mobile view | Desktop view. Terms and Conditions;

genomebiology.com/2015/16/1/50

3Novices: Genetically modified people / 3novicesaustralia

Alastair Crisp and Chiara Boschetti of Cambridge University, ... just published in **Genome Biology**, suggest human beings have at least 145 genes picked up from other species by their forebears. Admittedly, ... Dr **Crisp** and Dr **Boschetti** came to this conclusion by ...

3novicesaustralia.wordpress.com/2015/03/13/3novicesgenetically-modified-p...

University of Cambridge (via noodls) / Human genome includes ...

Lead author **Alastair Crisp** from the Department of Chemical Engineering and Biotechnology at the **University of Cambridge** said: ... **Genome Biology**; 12 March 2015. Smartlinks | **University of Cambridge** ...

noodls.com/viewNoodl/27279104/university-of-cambridg...

PLOS Genetics: Biochemical Diversification through Foreign ...

Contributed equally to this work with: **Chiara Boschetti**, Adrian Carr, **Alastair Crisp** Affiliation: Department of Chemical Engineering and Biotechnology, **University of Cambridge, Cambridge, United Kingdom**

journals.plos.org/plosgenetics/article?id=10.1371/journal.p...

Some genes 'foreign' in origin and not from our ancestors

Lead author **Alastair Crisp** from the **University of Cambridge, UK**, ... **Alastair Crisp, Chiara Boschetti**, ... Expression of multiple horizontally acquired genes is a hallmark of both vertebrate and invertebrate genomes, **Genome Biology** 2015.

phys.org/news/2015-03-genes-foreign-ancestors.html

Some genes 'foreign' in origin and not from our ancestors ...

Lead author **Alastair Crisp** from the **University of Cambridge, UK**, ... **Alastair Crisp, Chiara Boschetti, Malcolm Perry**, ... **Genome Biology** serves the biological research community as an international forum for the dissemination, ...

evesdrift.com/2015/03/12/some-genes-foreign-in-origin-a...

Tenth of quirky creature's active genes are foreign: Believed ...

Tenth of quirky creature's active genes are foreign: ... lead author of the study from the **University of Cambridge**. ... **Chiara Boschetti**, Adrian Carr, **Alastair Crisp**, Isobel Eyres, Yuan Wang-Koh, Esther Lubzens, ...

sciencedaily.com/releases/2012/11/121115172032.htm

Rädertierchen lagern Sex aus : Scienceticker ...

... **Chiara Boschetti/University of Cambridge**. ... **Chiara Boschetti**, Adrian Carr, **Alastair Crisp** und Alan Tunnacliffe, ... Department of Genetics und **Cambridge Systems Biology Centre, University of Cambridge**; und andere. Veröffentlichung PLoS Genetics, ...

scienceticker.info/2012/11/16/radertierchen-lagern-sex-aus/

低温生物工学会誌Vol.58 No.1 : 低温生物学...

... **University of Cambridge**, **Chiara BOSCHETTI**, **Alastair CRISP**, ... **University of Cambridge**, ... Developmental, and Integrative **Biology**, Department of Biological Sciences, Louisiana State **University**, Steven C. **HAND**, Yuvraj **PATIL**, ...

> square.umin.ac.jp/jscc/jp/publication/journal/vol59_no1.html

Proposed Roll of the Regent House - **Cambridge University** ...

In accordance with Regulation 1 of the regulations for the Roll of the Regent House ... **Boschetti, Chiara**. Boss, Sally Ruth, CHU ... **Crisp**, Edmund **Alastair** David, SE. **Crisp** ...

admin.cam.ac.uk/reporter/2014-15/special/01/section7.shtml

6. Courtship raises male fertilization success through post-mating sexual selection in a spider

Jutta M. Schneider , Kristiani Lesmono

DOI: 10.1098/rspb.2009.0694 Published 24 July 2009

- [Article](#)
- [Figures & Data](#)
- [Info & Metrics](#)
- [eLetters](#)
- [PDF](#)

Abstract

Courtship is well known for its positive effects on mating success. However, in polyandrous species, sexual selection continues to operate after copulation. Cryptic female choice is expected under unpredictable mating rates in combination with sequential mate encounters. However, there are very few accounts of the effects of courtship on cryptic female choice, and the available evidence is often correlative.

Mature *Argiope bruennichi* females are always receptive and never attack or reject males before mating, although sexual cannibalism after mating occurs regularly. Still, males usually perform an energetic vibratory display prior to copulation. We tested the hypothesis that beneficial effects of courtship arise cryptically, during or

after mating, resulting in increased paternity success under polyandry.

Manipulating courtship duration experimentally, we found that males that mated without display had a reduced paternity share even though no differences in post-copulatory cannibalism or copulation duration were detected. This suggests that the paternity advantage associated with courtship arose through female-mediated processes after intromission, meeting the definition of cryptic female choice.

7.

The tremendous pace at which findings reach far corners of the scientific world is made possible by the web and augmented by social media.

REMARKABLE REACH

More than 3,000 scientists and engineers told Nature about their awareness of various giant social networks and research-profiling sites. Just under half said that they visit ResearchGate regularly. Another 480 respondents in the humanities, arts and social sciences were less keen on ResearchGate.

- I am aware of this site and visit regularly
- I am aware of this site but do not visit regularly
- I am not aware of this site

8.

Let us go back in time and see how it was 150 years ago.

On the alleged Expansion in Volume of various Substances in passing by Befirigeration from the state of Liquid Fusion to

that of Solidification. ^' By Robert Mallet^ F.R.S. &c. Received April 28, 1874*.

The fact that "water expands in becoming ice, and that the latter thus floats upon the water, can scarcely have escaped the observation or in->ference of the acute Intellects of a remote antiquity. Its conditions, when more carefully examined in modem times, pointed out the strange and, as it has been called, anomalous fact that water can be cooled 7^ or 8^ below its freezing-point without becoming solid, and that between its maximum density at about 39^ Fahr. and its freezing-point at 32° Fahr., or within the narrow range of 7° Fahr., it expands in the large ratio of 915 : 1000.

Standing thus alone amongst observed phenomena in nature, it seems to have suggested to many experimenters the question whether other bodies when liquefied by heat might not also expand when becoming solid by refrigeration. I have not attempted to trace with minuteness the history of past inquiry upon this subject, many loose uncertain statements as to which have for at least a century continued to perplex scientific literature. Reaumur appears to have been the first who gave currency to the statement that cast iron, bismuth, and antimony all expand in consolidating. The like fact has been alleged or left to be inferred with respect to the following substances by the authorities named : —

Silver, Fersoz.

Copper, Karsten.

Mercury and Gold, as inferred by Nasmyth and Carpenter.

* Rvd June 11, 1874. See * Proceedings,' vol. xxi. p. 366.

It may be taken as a typical or medium example of all good grey cast irons. I have not been enabled to repeat this experiment with the white, rigid, and crystalline cast irons, such as are employed for projectiles and other purposes ; but as it is a recognized fact amongst iron-founders that these irons expand in the range of temperature between solidity and liquidity much more than do grey irons, so we may justifiably conclude that the decrease of specific gravity by fusion of these hard cast irons would be in even a greater ratio than that shown by the above experiment on grey iron ; and generally the author feels himself justified in concluding that it is not true that any cast iron is denser in the fused than in the solid state. Cold cast iron, therefore, does not float upon liquid cast iron of the same quality by reason of its buoyancy, but in virtue of some force which tends to keep it upon the surface of the molten metal in opposition to a very considerable want of buoyancy or tendency to sink by greater density on the part of the solid iron, which is, by the preceding results, $\frac{1}{10}$ of its weight, whatever that may be, and is probably even greater than this in the case of hard white cast irons. The author's chief object has been thus far rather to prove that the cause assigned by the writers already

mentioned is not the true cause of the floating of solid upon liquid cast iron of the same quality.

The British Journal for the History of Science

[The British Journal for the History of Science](#) / Volume 2 / Issue 04 / December 1965, pp **360-361**

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DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1017/S0007087400002557> ([About DOI](#)),

Published online: 05 January **2009**

[Table of Contents - 1965 - Volume 2, Issue 04](#)

[Author Index](#)

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Book Reviews

A History of Scientific and Technical Periodicals: The Origins and Development of the Scientific and Technological Press 1665–1790. By David A. Kronick. Pp. 274; tables. New York: The Scarecrow Press, 1962. \$6.50.

J. A. Chaldecott

Here are a few sites you might want to visit:

http://www.uri.edu/artsci/com/Logan/teaching/html/wrt333/notes/Gross_Communicating_Sciencehtm.htm

<http://www.theguardian.com/higher-education-network/gallery/2015/feb/12/philosophical-transactions-of-the-royal-society-350-years-of-science-publishing-in-pictures>

<https://royalsociety.org/events/2014/12/pubs-350-exhibition/>

Change in narrative styles

Changes in technology

Rise in the volume of research and diversity of fields and styles of doing research

A paper from arXiv dated 13 Mar 2015:

<http://arxiv.org/pdf/1503.03568.pdf>

To illustrate TeX and technical drawing of figures in one go.

The power of technology is becoming even more evident in recent years.

1997 IBM's Deep Blue defeats Kasparov

2011 INM's Watson defeated two champions in the quiz programme 'Jeopardy.'

AP stories on company earnings now can be written – data gathering, analysis and writing – by a bot, patented by Automated Insights.

Another company 'Narrative Science' expects that their programme can write a story that can win the Pulitzer Prize.